

Improving the accuracy of earthquake risk estimates with OpenStreetMap building data

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Seismic risk models provide an estimation of human and building loss and damage due to earthquakes. They help decision makers to better prepare and plan for earthquakes as well as to better understand and manage the post-disaster phase. Thus the more certain and accurate the risk assessments, the more likely they can contribute to a successful disaster management after an event.

The famous statement “Earthquakes don’t kill, buildings do!” refers to the fact that knowing the location and earthquake-relevant properties of buildings is crucial. Depending on the distance from the epicenter, the main construction material, the height, etc., each building reacts differently when exposed to the shaking created by an earthquake, called the earthquake hazard. Exposure models describe the built environment, usually as the number and distribution of building types and are created for entire countries from census data in collaboration with engineers. By combining such models with OpenStreetMap (OSM) data, we create exposure models that also provide the location of buildings. OSM has been used in the past for augmenting exposure models, for example, Figueiredo and Martina [1] used OSM to improve the quality of the exposure models and Sousa et al. [2] used OSM to propose a method to create a building-specific exposure model for industrial buildings in Europe. We also assign vulnerabilities to each building type describing the expected damage grade depending on the level of shaking. Combining hazard, exposure and vulnerability leads to seismic risk, a description of the expected damage and losses due to earthquakes. For damage and loss assessments done after an earthquake, with the hazard being reliably measured in terms of shaking intensity, the exposure model is the element with the largest uncertainty. This confirms the need to know as much as possible about the distribution and types of buildings in hazard-prone areas.

Thus to increase the accuracy of the risk assessments, we need to increase the accuracy of the exposure model. The exposure models used in this study are building-by-building exposure models covering various countries in Europe (Albania, Andorra,

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Austria, Belgium, Switzerland, Czech Republic, Greece, Italy, and Turkey), created by taking the building locations from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and the possible types for each building from census data. These types were published by *The European Facilities for Earthquake Hazard and Risk* (EFEHR, www.efehr.org) for Europe in the framework of the European Seismic Risk Model 2020 [3]. Here, we focus on studying the building information taken from OSM that can improve the accuracy of detecting building types in the exposure model. Knowing the type of buildings is an important aspect of exposure models, because the risk-related behavior of buildings is dependent on it.

Each building type is defined using the Building Taxonomy of the Global Earthquake Model [4] describing all relevant features of buildings in a systematic way, such as the main construction material, lateral load resistance system, occupancy and number of stories. Using the census data, each building in the exposure model is assigned in a probabilistic approach with numerous possible types due to lack of information about the respective building. This means that having information about particular features of individual buildings can help us narrow down the possible types assigned to a building by eliminating some of the types that do not match with the building properties and gets us closer to the exact type of the building. This results in increasing the accuracy on the building-type detection aspect of the exposure model.

From OSM we obtain the number of stories and derive occupancy information for each individual building where available. This way, as pointed out above, for each building we can omit the building types assigned to that building that do not match the number of stories and occupancy information taken from OSM and be left with fewer numbers of possible types. The fewer the number of possible types for a building, the more certain we are about the building type.

To study the effect of each of the OSM building properties (number of stories and occupancy), we create the building-specific exposure model four times, using different sets of information. The first model, named the *Basic* model, consists of building polygons, taken from OSM and the possible building types taken from the census data. In this model, each building comprises the full probability distribution of all possible types as reported in the census data for the region the building is located in. This model does not increase the knowledge about building types compared to a classical exposure model but adds exact building locations to the model. The next model, named the *Stories* model, is the *Basic* model enriched with the information about the number of stories per building. This means that the possible types for each building are reduced to the types matching the number of its stories. Another model, named the *Occupancy* model, is the *Basic* model enriched with the occupancy information and again only using the possible types per building that match its occupancy. Finally, the last model, named the *Standard* model, is the *Basic* model but using the full set of information, both occupancy and number of stories.

We observe that the total number of possible types for all the buildings decreases significantly when using OSM information (in the *Occupancy*, *Stories* and *Standard* models) compared to the *Basic* model, among which, unsurprisingly, the *Standard* model contains the lowest number of types. The reduction observed in the *Occupancy* model compared to the *Stories* model is larger due the fact that the occupancy is by far a more available property compared to the number of stories, which can result in a judgment bias.

To remove the bias resulting from the unequal number of buildings carrying information about occupancy and number of stories, we introduce the Reduction Factor (RF).

The RF is defined as the total number of types for the buildings that include a specific information (either number of stories or occupancy or both) divided by the total number of types for the same buildings in the *Basic* model, ignoring the buildings for which no further information is available, to better quantify the effect of adding these properties to OSM. As an example, the RF value for Greece is 0.3, 0.53, 0.15 for the *Stories*, *Occupancy* and *Standard* model, respectively. An RF value of 0.15 for the *Standard* model for Greece means that the buildings carrying occupancy and number of stories in Greece are on average left with only 15% of the types they are initially assigned with, in absence of the occupancy and number of stories (as in the *Basic* model).

Therefore, the number of stories reduces the possible types for a building more than the occupancy information on average per building in Greece. Thus adding the number of stories to buildings can significantly increase the accuracy of the type compared to adding occupancy information. However, both number of stories and occupancy lead to the largest reduction and thus to a significant improvement of exposure models. We observed and report on similar results for all the countries studied except Andorra and the Czech Republic. The highest RF for the *Standard* model among the countries studied belongs to Switzerland with 0.31 and the lowest belongs to Croatia, with 0.10.

The accuracy of an earthquake loss assessment depends on the accuracy of the measured hazard intensity, the exposure and the vulnerability model. Addition of building information to the exposure model, results in more accurate choice of vulnerability functions. Therefore, with a better prediction of the vulnerability class of the buildings, we move from an average to a more accurate, building-specific loss assessment (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The probability of slight damage computed for a scenario similar to the M6.0 1999 Athens earthquake. The frames cover the area of Piraeus, Greece, and show the damage probability only for the

buildings that carry the number of stories and occupancy properties. Each frame represents one of the four models, *Basic* (top left), *Stories* (top right), *Occupancy* (bottom left) and *Standard* model (bottom right). The darker the color, the higher the probability of slight damage. Please note that the exact values are not provided to protect personal identifiable information.

It should be mentioned that information about the age of a building, its construction material and other building properties would benefit exposure models even further. However, they are usually not found in OSM. This is why we have limited this study to the most common building features that can either be found in OSM (number of stories) or derived from other pieces of information (occupancy).

This study shows the power of Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI), specifically OSM, in increasing the accuracy of detecting building types that results in improving the accuracy of resulting risk assessments that are of great importance for both preparing for and coping with earthquake disasters. Besides, this study points out that activities towards mapping the number of stories or the building occupancy can help significantly improve the quality of exposure data and subsequently the loss and damage assessment of an earthquake disaster. New tools like StreetComplete (<https://streetcomplete.app>) or Every Door (<https://every-door.app>) make the collection of building properties very easy and have already contributed significantly to the growth of the number of buildings with more properties provided. A possible reason for the overall lack of building properties is the fact that these are not visible on the standard map provided by OSM and thus not providing a clear incentive to collect such data. Specific maps that highlight more building properties could provide such an incentive. Because exposure models are not used solely for earthquake loss assessments, Evaz Zadeh et al. [5] showed first applications of such a detailed exposure model in the scope of multi-hazard risk assessment. In particular, for floods and tsunamis the building locations are very important and exposure models not providing the exact locations of buildings are prone to produce wrong assessments. Thus, the OSM building dataset is already a great augmentation to exposure models and will get better with more building properties being collected.

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